

Policy Brief 2025/002
February 24th, 2025
By Christophe Barclay

Issue/problem

The US National Institute of Health (NIH) [announced](#) that it has capped the indirect cost rate provided in its grants, significantly cutting university funds used to cover research infrastructure.

Description of the problem

As [the largest public funder of biomedical research](#), the NIH plays an important role in allocating funds to the development pharmaceutical and innovation. Direct costs are used by the research team to pay for [salaries and supplies](#), while indirect costs maintain university infrastructure necessary for the research. The NIH will now cap the indirect cost rate at 15% down from an average of 27% — with certain institutions having indirect cost rates as high as [69%](#).

Results

The NIH claims that this change brings the indirect cost rate in line with private funding and should not affect US innovation. However, [multiple associations](#) of [American universities](#) claim that this will drastically limit their capability to fund and continue research into pharmaceutical innovation, and undermine the United States' competitive advantage in innovation.

The NIH's guidance is currently subject to a temporary [restraining order](#). This is an interim measure until the federal judge can decide on the legality of the NIH's guidance. Until then, the prior indirect funding rate continues.

Lessons learned

In [2017](#), the first Trump administration attempted to cap the NIH indirect rate at 10% amongst other cuts to research funding in its budget proposal. However, this was blocked by the Senate and Congress. The current indirect cost rate cut stems from an executive order directly cutting funding to federal agencies.

The NIH has historically played a [key role](#) in [funding](#) American innovation, especially for [early-career scientists](#). However, certain research shows that research universities are able to [substitute](#) public funds to maintain the same research levels. However, the study in question did not consider funding cuts as drastic as the one currently proposed. Current indirect funding rates for Canadian universities are lower than the previous NIH indirect funding rate but higher than the current rate.